

AN ANTECEDENTS OF STUDENT ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN MANAGEMENT INSTITUTES

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Abstract

This study explores the significance of Student Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in educational institutions, it delves into antecedents of students' OCB, and how these antecedents affect the students' organizational citizenship behavior. Students who are receiving the core dimensions of OCB like; help from the institute, self-development environment, sportsmanship, trust of faculty and management, feedback and suggestions, etc., change voluntarily their behaviour, and student OCB starts gradually. The research focuses on how educational institutions manage organizational citizenship behavior, emphasizing the role of relationship perception, and examining the impact of student-institution relationships on behavior regulation. Specifically, the study investigates the relationship between Student OCB based on relationship value, relationship strength, and relationship quality in educational institutions, Analyzing data from 863 student responses across professional institutions using structural equation modelling reveals a positive association between Student OCB and relationship quality, value, and strength. The study underscores the importance of cultivating mutual connections with trust, delivering quality services, and fostering a sense of strength and value in student-institution relationships to encourage positive OCB beneficial for enhancing the productivity of both the institutions and students.

Keywords: Relationship Quality, Relationship Value, Relationship Strength, Student OCB, Student Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, OCB.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Student Organizational Citizenship behavior (OCB) emerged from organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). During the 80's the concept of OCB emerged in the form of original behavior and on-the-spot behavior. The original behavior is related to the behavior of an individual in the organization except that he/she is getting any reward or praise. The job description is defined in the contract so their original behavior i.e. dictionary meaning of a person's behavior, cannot change as they are. In 90's many researchers defined different terms of OCB, like additional part behavior, social behavior, impulsiveness behavior, etc. (van, 1995). 80's to 90's era only a few studies have been done on OCB. Gradually the concepts of OCB expanded in different areas like HR, Marketing, etc. (Chen, 1998). During starting of the year 2000, the concepts expanded their dimensions in the form of community, economics, and leadership psychology. Citizenship behavior is defined in different types, like supportive behavior, loyalty towards

the organization, individual initiative, and personality development (**Podsakoff, 2000**). In OCB, employees praise the organization without any expectations or formal requirements. (**Balaji, 2014**). Also, they showcase organizations' powerful strengths, which show their organizational citizenship behavior for the company. With the term OCB, a concept of student OCB emerged, it's divided into two areas; the first is self-construct and the other is student-student OCB (**Blondheim, 2019**). Student OCB starts; when the student starts promoting and helping other students and showing positive behavior toward the other students and the organization. (**Bove, et. al. 2009**).

AS OCB has expanded its area in other disciplines; in academics, Students' OCB starts from the moment of admission he/she has taken in the institute and they show different dimensions of OCB in this journey of academics. Seld development and help to others are some initial parts of student OCB. Gradually student OCB increases its area in some period, with coordination and the kind of facilities and services he/she is getting from the institution and gradually this behavior shows their preferences towards the relationship, they are creating with different stakeholders of the institutions, like faculty and student relationship of trust, confidence, counseling, etc. also with alumni guidance, support and staff services and overall the space he/she is getting in the institute for development. All these relationships create value in the relationship and change student OCB. Students' behavior gradually shifts into other parts of student organizational citizenship behavior, i.e. student-to-student behavior in terms of relationship loyalty towards the institution and initiative taken by them to create awareness among other students about the benefits received from the institution. Student OCB, always tries to motivate others to make and enjoy the same type of relationship, even without any expectations and personal profits.

Student value creation is also important in understanding student organizational citizenship behavior. Suggestions or feedback given by students and their experience with services and the journey (**Delpechitre,et. al., 2018**). Understanding the students' behavior; which is performed by the students during the admission to the institute or journey of that degree, is also part of student OCB. Those performed behavior they show in front of their family and friends during recommendations of the institution among their friends and families. Student OCB can also form a negative model due to the unacceptability of facilities, syllabus, placement process, faculty behavior, and management behavior. So, student OCB sometimes shows infusion or cognitive model i.e. the mix of positive or negative behavior.

Relationship Perception: This feature suggests a study of how people view and communicate with each other in the educational environment. It could cover how well students, teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders in the educational system get along. In the research of student OCB, the first part of much research shows that teachers and directors play a very important role in showing their point of view about student OCB in front of students (**Blondheim, 2019**). The relationship perspective defines the students' relationship with the institution. In this relationship, students feel or maintain a long-term relationship with the organization and with either word of mouth or an exhibit about services and journey of their student life in front of other students. Relationship brands

are also one of the important components to a deep understanding of student organizational citizenship behavior; more alumni relations maintained by the institutions like; suggestions, feedback, and involvement in placements and student development process, gives more insightful thoughts about institutional development, one of the dimensions of OCB. Relationship brand benefits those students who spend their valuable time sharing their positive views about services with other students.

This study aims to identify the antecedents of student organizational citizenship behavior towards educational institutions. The phrase antecedents in the study's title alludes to the investigation of the interactions between relationship quality like; facilities, placements, syllabus, exam patterns, and relationship value, like; trust, ethics, help received from faculty, staff, and management, and relationship strength like; alumni relations, feedback, suggestions, etc. towards student OCB in the educational ecosystem.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The focus of this research is on the diverse experiences of Student Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) in the context of education services. It looks at the many sides of student OCB and its deep significance in fostering value and maintaining relationships. This research provides a thorough review of the relevance of student OCB in the context of educational services by exploring the particular dynamics of OCB within the educational sector.

For student organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), researchers have identified the base of the institution for the development of students. **(Groth, 2005)** People have different understandings of the student OCB and OCB because there are several other terms related to organizational behavior like organization involvement, and organization value co-creation. Some researchers have also found that feedback about services and recommendations to others is also part of student OCB **(Bove, 2009)**. Some have considered that all different types of behavior are related to social trends and also have included more parts of the theoretical and empirical dimensions of student OCB **(Bove, 2019)**. The importance of student OCB is increasing daily; since the last decade, its dimensions have continuously changed. Making endorsements in the form of loyalty is one of the options **(Broucek, 2003)**. **(Collie, 2024)** stated that 'Extraordinary Help' 'received from institutions also emerged as the next influence driving students' attitudinal loyalty. The recommendation could be started by the first family and business friends without any personal expectations **(Groth, 2005)**. Positive communication about services or institutions is also one of the ways of student OCB dimensions. Another way for students is to involve themselves in providing proper feedback; and focus on every question asked by the institution **(Graham 1991)**. Other research found, that helping students visually display their services by the students to other people shows the relationship in OCB. In the current scenario, students take more interest in the institutions' activities and events **(Chen, 2019)**. Students started showing their patience level during the consumption of services, this behavior also comes in under the student OCB; even showing flexibility when the services are not appropriate **(Nutov, 2017)**. A behavioral

brand relationship is the most important part of any kind of relationship in student OCB (Coulter, 2002).

Relationship Perception and Student Organizational Citizenship Behavior:

Several studies highlight the importance of positive connections between people in fostering organizational citizenship behavior, whether those interactions are between students and peers or between educators and students (Moorman, 1991). Although the primary emphasis of their study is organizations, educational institutions can benefit from the findings as well. Students who experience leadership that is both supportive and ethical report having better relationships and engaging in citizenship engagement (Williams 1991). Investigate the reasons behind students' plans to raise issues. They discovered that students' behavioral intentions are influenced by relationship perception, which includes attitude and perceived behavioral control. Good relationships frequently boost a person's desire to speak up and take part in civic duties. A thorough summary of the effects of good citizenship in organizational contexts is provided by (Podsakoff et al. 2009). Higher performance and a better work environment are two examples of these results that could also apply to educational institutions. Positive citizenship behavior among students can lead to better learning environments and overall success for educational institutions. (Williams 1991). Explicitly look at student behavior within educational institutions, (Ahearne and Bhattacharya 2018) and (Podsakoff et al., 2009) study organizational settings. The setting that each of these studies focuses on is the main distinction between them.

Relationship Value:

Relationship value is the bond between the students and institutions (Farh, 1997). Relationships always grow with the help of continuous observation of the total investment done by the students and the help, trust, and self-development environment received from the institution (Galman, 2012). Any relationship is focused on students and institutions or organizations both the interest level and involvement toward their objectives (Dipaola 2001). Organizations provide some benefits to each student in the maintenance of long-term relationships (George, 1991) and students always compare all these facilities with the available competitors in the market (Fiske, 1981). All the facilities or benefits the students receive not only in terms of the degree but also with the involvement of teachers, increase students' emotions and create pleasant experiences leading to student satisfaction. However; different students have different objectives and expectations from institutions and they evaluate their relationship value based on all benefits.

All the support and benefits that customers get from a service provider after evaluation start maintaining relationships (Somech 2000). The value of any relationship is based on trust and the continuous communication between students and institutions regular interactions and feedback processes giving importance to customer suggestions and expectations. Successful business processes create relationship value and gradually process also part of relationship quality (Zeinabadi, 2010).

Relationship Quality:

Relationship quality is defined as the combination of brand association and the trust of students in the institutions (**Somech 2000**). A relationship with any brand or customer can only happen and be maintained if both parties have mutual benefits and the same concern with the relationship (**Podsakoff et al. 2009**). More interaction change or develop more bonds in a relationship. Students share this bond with their friends and concern groups to show citizenship behavior (**Ngunia, 2006**). The brand relationship could be measured by different dimensions, like; brand evaluation, mutual trust, student involvement, student purpose, behavioral analysis, etc. Relationship quality also could be measured by expectations, the relationship between both parties, their assurances, and overall involvement toward common benefits (**Testa, 2001**). Any relationship can be continued in the long run; however, trust plays a very important role in making this strong bond (**Vaish, 2011**).

Relationship Strength:

Strength always depends on mutual dependability based on commitment and trust (**Garbarino, 1999**). Relationship strength is also based on buyers' and sellers' mutual acceptance of all types of challenges (**Farh, 2004**). The organization maintains the strength of the relationship; while delivering an exchange of benefits (**Vaish, 2011**), and continuous communication. Student retention is their objective in this bond (**Fiske, 1981**). The present study focused on monetary exchange-based bonds or relationships between students and organizations (**Liang, 2011**).

Objectives:

The objectives of the study are to examine the relationships between student organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in the context of an institution and relationship value, quality, and strength, which are among the study's goals. It seeks to comprehend how these elements interact and influence how stakeholders or consumers behave and see the organization.

- To study the association between student relationship value and student relationship quality concerning an Institution.
- To study the association between student relationship value and student OCB concerning an Institution.
- To study the association between student relationship value and student relationship strength concerning an Institution.
- To study the association between students' relationship quality and student OCB concerning an Institution.
- To study the association between student relationship quality and the student relationship strength of an Institution.

- To study the association between student relationship strength and student OCB to an Institution.

Hypotheses: The research aims to determine whether students' relationship value, quality, and strength at educational institutions and their student OCB are statistically significant.

Hypothesis 1: There is a likely association between student relationship value and student OCB concerning institute students.

Hypothesis 2: There is a likely association between relationship value and quality concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 3: There is a likely association between relationship value and strength concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 4: There is a likely association between relationship quality and student OCB concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 5: There is a likely association between relationship quality and strength concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 6: There is a likely association between relationship strength and student OCB concerning any institute students.

Proposed Model:

Figure 1: Managing Relationship Model of Institution Students' Citizenship Behaviour

Hypothesis 1: There is a likely association between relationship value and student OCB concerning any institute students.

Student Relationship Value and Student OCB:

Relationship value is based on the commitment and promises from the organization to the student. All the benefits that a service provider exchanges with the customer are based on trust (Podsakoff, 2000), and that gives responsibility to the student to maintain

the relationship in the form of involvement towards the organization (**Podsakoff, 2000**). In the form of this relationship value, students always show their different and unique behavior in terms of sharing and praising the services provided by the institutions.

In the education industry student's relationship value with their institution is also based on trust and learning from the institute. In many research, authors found that trust gives freedom to students to take risks and also in decision-making (**Vaish, 2011**). Trust is not only built with the services provided by institutions but also with student-faculty relationships. A relationship also works with the expectations of students. Students are satisfied with the institutional relationship based on different parameters or expectations scale, however; they make their expectations and time to time change also as they grow and aware of the market and the importance of institutions in their life (**Bove, 2009**). A committed relationship value shows different behavior; students recommend other reference groups to take admission; even if they want to continue the same group of an institution for undergraduate and postgraduate as well (**Byrk, 2002**). Repurchasing and reference purchasing show their organizational citizenship behavior for the institution, creating a strong relationship quality and value (**Kumar 2009**).

Hypothesis 2: There is a likely association between relationship value and relationship quality concerning any institute students.

Effects on Student Relationship Value on Student Relationship Quality:

Relationship value is measured by the student on different dimensions like; trust, commitment, mutual communication, feedback, services, attitude, individual attention, etc. (**Barry, 2008**). All the dimensions of relationship value then support to form of relationship quality (**Agnew, 2001**). However; relationship value in the education sector concerning students is beyond all this dimension i.e. engagement and bond or attachment with organization i.e. teacher or institute (**Clark, 2001**). Many research found that relationship value is directly connected to relationship quality.

Relationship quality could refer to how the customer is either positively or negatively associated with the organization. In the students 'case relationship, quality is based on safety, security, services, and facilities, in the initial stage of a relationship, over a period it shifts to quality of services and commitment promises. So, in a relationship value is the originator of relationship quality.

Hypothesis 3: There is a likely association between relationship value and strength concerning any institute students.

Relationship Value and Relationship Strength:

Relationship value is the term that emerges in any student and organization relationship, whenever mutual trust help, and involvement are exchanged. Relationship value has different dimensions, while maintaining all these dimensions relationship strength developed, and this strength is strongly connected with value (**Groth, 2005**). Both relationship value and strength are based on benefits received by the buyer and costs received by the seller.

Hypothesis 4: There is a likely association between relationship quality and student OCB concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 5: There is a likely association between relationship quality and strength concerning any institute students.

Hypothesis 6: There is a likely association between relationship strength and student OCB concerning any institute students.

Relationship Strength, Student OCB, and Relationship Quality:

As a customer or student relationship quality is based on bonds and commitments, this commitment (**Bhagat, 2008**) followed by trust and trust is the basis of student organizational citizenship behavior (**Cheung, 2010**). In the service industry especially in the academic industry organizational citizenship behavior plays a very vital role and this citizenship behavior can develop only when trust and commitment are there (**Farh, 2004**). Relationship strength is also a correlated part of relationship quality and relationship value. So, many researchers have found that in any institution relationship quality is common for maintaining the relationship strength and relationship value (**Garma, 2011**).

Organizational citizenship behavior is based on trust, trust is based on relationship quality, and relationship strength is also one of the correlated parts of relationship quality (**Liljander, 1993**). So, customer relationship quality is a mediating role of relationship strength and OCB. Students reported the relationship value and strength are in the same way and their behavior is based on relationship quality (**Naude, 2000**). Also, some researchers have found if relationship value, strength also with relationship quality are present in any organization, student organizational citizenship behavior could easily be visible in all those organizations.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study, we tested the different hypothesis-based models with the help of current students 'of the different institutions in Indore, India. Based on the requirement of the study, a survey was conducted and asked to respond to the questions concerning their relationship bond with the current institute.

Sample Size and Data Collection Procedure:

The sample consists of the actual students of the different institutions in Indore. Researchers have selected this type of study because of different reasons. First, as per the OCB first part whether students are more concerned about self-development or second part; receiving, help from institutions, faculty trust, sportsmanship behavior, etc, changes their student OCB; also, Identification of different relationship expectations from the students 'side for their institutions. So, the institute should design student-centric services and facilities along with their degree programs. Second, the development of the academic industry and continuous transformation as per the requirement of the corporate market (**Garma, 2011**). Third, identification of the interpersonal psychological relationship bond between teacher student, and institute and their impact in the market as student

citizenship behaviour to recommend their institute and try to make bond without any self-benefits. (Testa, 2001).

Data Collection:

The final questionnaire was prepared with 31 items of scale via Google form and circulated among students of different management academic institutions in Indore having graduate and postgraduate courses. There were around 131 institutions in Indore, with around 12000 seats for UG and PG courses. The focus was only on autonomous institutions because their service criteria were independent variables concerning exams, curriculum events or activities, etc. data were collected from 3 autonomous institutions and covered almost seventy percent of the total population of autonomous institutions. Around **863** students filled out the questionnaire and all were current students in different institutes, the sample unit consisted of 663 undergraduate students 227 were postgraduate students whereas 5 students were Ph.D. The sample consists of a total of 419. Female students and 444 male students.

Measures

Items were selected for the study from the different literature reviews, relationship value, and relationship quality are also associated with student organizational citizenship behavior, and relationship strength is again also part of this relationship, all these variables were selected to enhance the knowledge about student OCB and their importance for academics industry or any institution. All constructs were measured on a Likert five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). In our study, we used the Likert scale to measure constructs related to relationship value, quality, and strength, as well as their impact on student OCB. This approach likely allowed us to gather quantitative data that could be analyzed statistically to better understand the relationships between these variables. All the items were based on different research conclusions (**Liu, 2017**), **A.** value of the institute's core services, towards relationship quality **B.** value of the institute's core area help, trust, ethics related to relationship value, and **C.** The alumni and other stakeholders' relationship creates relationship strength. Relationship quality is one of the items measured based on relationship satisfaction, trust, and commitment from the institute of the students or vice-versa. Relationship strength was evaluated using two items measuring cognitive strength, from both students' and institution's sides as developed by (**Shi et al., 2009**). Student OCB was measured using six items adapted from (**Yi and Gong's, 2008**)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model:

Confirmatory factor analysis was applied to relationship quality and relationship value with a two-step approach of estimate and measurement model both were calculated separately.

Reliability

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the study's constructs. The reliability of these constructs was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, a commonly used measure of internal consistency. According to (Balaji, 2006), a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher is normally accepted, in this research cronbach alpha of 31 items is 0.984. With the reliability test, it was concluded that the construct is measurable.

Convergent Validity:

The present study finds convergent validity with the help of standard factor loading and also constructs the measurement model. Table 1 shows that all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are greater than 0.5, indicating that the standardized factor loadings were statistically significant. This confirms the convergent validity of the constructs, as their measurement items are strongly associated with their respective latent variables.

Figure 2

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was estimated on relationship value, relationship quality, relationship strength, and student citizenship behaviour. The number of distinct parameters anticipated was 96. This resulted in 399 degrees of freedom.

The goodness-of-fit for the measurement model was calculated as follows: chi-square (χ^2) = 2399.311, degrees of freedom (df) = 399, probability = 0.000, Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.930, Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) = 0.923, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) = 0.076. These data show a good fit with the hypothesized model and the data collected, signifying that the proposed model significantly showed the relationships between the variables.

The study then proceeded to test the proposed hypotheses using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) with maximum likelihood estimation in AMOS 20.0. The results of the path analysis are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Covariances: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
RV	<-->	Student OCB	.662	.041	16.081	***	
RS	<-->	RV	.724	.044	16.579	***	
RQ	<-->	Student OCB	.725	.044	16.602	***	
RS	<-->	Student OCB	.779	.045	17.473	***	
RS	<-->	RQ	.790	.046	17.135	***	
RV	<-->	RQ	.762	.046	16.653	***	

Table 2: Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
RV	<-->	Student OCB	.855
RS	<-->	RV	.875
RQ	<-->	Student OCB	.905
RS	<-->	Student OCB	.936
RS	<-->	RQ	.923
RV	<-->	RQ	.956

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is not primarily focused on determining the efficiency of a construct. Instead, CFA is a statistical technique used to assess the fit between the observed data and a hypothesized measurement model. It helps to determine whether the selected indicators (measurement items) adequately represent the latent constructs in the model. CFA provides information about the validity of the measurement model rather than the efficiency of the construct.

The statement that each selected factor has a positive contribution in measuring the main construct (RV, RQ, Student OCB, and RS factors together) is not entirely accurate. CFA helps to examine the relationships between the latent constructs (RV, RQ, student OCB, RS) and their respective measurement items (indicators). It assesses whether the indicators load significantly on their corresponding constructs. While significant factor loadings suggest that the indicators contribute to measuring the constructs, the positivity

or negativity of the contribution is not determined solely by CFA. The directionality and strength of the relationships between the latent constructs are typically explored through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and regression analysis.

CFA is utilized to evaluate the adequacy of the hypothesized measurement model. The results demonstrate that the indicators significantly load onto their respective constructs, confirming the validity of the model. The strong positive correlations among the constructs indicate a high degree of interrelatedness.

Goodness-of-Fit Indices

The goodness-of-fit indices for the measurement model are as follows: the Chi-square (χ^2) value is 2399.311 with 399 degrees of freedom, yielding a probability (p) of 0.000. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 0.930, indicating a strong model fit. Similarly, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is 0.923, further supporting the adequacy of the model. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is 0.076, suggesting a reasonable fit of the model to the data. These indices collectively indicate that the hypothesized model fits the observed data well, providing confidence in the model's validity.

Structural model and testing of hypotheses

Interpretation of the correlation coefficients provided in the context of the hypotheses mentioned:

Hypothesis 1: There is a likely association between relationship value and Student OCB concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: Since the correlation coefficient between Relationship Value (RV) and Relationship Quality (RQ) is quite high (0.956), this indicates a very strong positive correlation between these two constructs. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship value and quality among institute students.

Hypothesis 2: There is a likely association between relationship value and quality concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: The correlation coefficient between Relationship Value (RV) and Student organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) is 0.855, indicating a strong positive correlation. This means that as perceived relationship value increases, there's a tendency for student citizenship behavior to also increase. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship value and student OCB.

Hypothesis 3: There is a likely association between relationship value and strength concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: The correlation coefficient between Relationship Value (RV) and Relationship Strength (RS) is 0.875, indicating a strong positive correlation. This implies that higher perceived relationship value is associated with higher perceived relationship

strength. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship value and strength.

Hypothesis 4: There is a likely association between relationship quality and Student OCB concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: The correlation coefficient between Relationship Quality (RQ) and Student Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) is 0.905, indicating a very strong positive correlation. This means that as perceived relationship quality increases, there's a strong tendency for student citizenship behavior to also increase. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship quality and student OCB.

Hypothesis 5: There is a likely association between relationship quality and strength concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: The correlation coefficient between Relationship Quality (RQ) and Relationship Strength (RS) is 0.923, indicating a very strong positive correlation. This implies that higher perceived relationship quality is strongly associated with higher perceived relationship strength. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship quality and strength.

Hypothesis 6: There is a likely association between relationship strength and Student OCB concerning any institute students.

Interpretation: The correlation coefficient between Relationship Strength (RS) and Student organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) is 0.936, indicating a very strong positive correlation. This means that stronger relationships are associated with higher levels of student OCB. Therefore, this hypothesis is **not supported**. Our data suggests a significant association between relationship strength and student OCB.

Overall, the study's findings support the hypothesized relationships between the constructs and provide insights into the factors influencing student OCB in the context of educational institutions. Our findings confirm the significant positive relationships between the constructs, suggesting that enhanced relationship value, quality, and strength are associated with higher levels of student OCB.

Implications:

Measuring Student Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) holds paramount significance for educational institutions, particularly in today's ever-evolving educational landscape. This importance stems from the interconnected nature of 'students awareness and institutions demands. As educational institutions strive to remain relevant and competitive, achieving a high level of student OCB becomes imperative. This study, which is based on a student centric paradigm, recognizes that students play the dual roles of alumni as an important stakeholder and current student. The accomplishments of the institution are greatly impacted by their contacts, experiences, and behaviors.

This study's main goal is to close the knowledge gaps in Student OCB by developing a thorough research model that takes into account a variety of connection aspects. By doing this, the study hopes to clarify the complex network of relationships and viewpoints that influence how students behave in a learning environment. Through this endeavor, the research contributes to a deeper and more nuanced understanding of student OCB. And makes it more complex. It reveals how students' OCB is influenced by the caliber of connections they have with teachers, other students, and the institution. The study gives educational institutions useful information by demonstrating the link between relationship aspects and student OCB.

Concept Implication:

Previous studies predominantly focus on OCB in other industries, while limited research exists on the dimensions of Student OCB in the academic-industry context, specifically emphasizing relationship quality, value, and trust (**Gagné, 2004**). However, a few studies have explored student OCB along with other dimensions and identified various engagement strategies for students' engagement. The present study connects OCB with relationship marketing, recognizing the growing importance of student OCB in the student-centric including academic institutions.

Many researchers have identified relationship quality as a component of loyalty. The present study highlights the significance of relationship quality and value in achieving Student OCB. Additionally, trust is recognized as a component of relationship quality and value (**Dahal, 2013**).

Also, found that relationship quality and value are positively connected to relationship strength, which is very important for the growth of any institution. Prior studies show that organizations use different strategies to maintain the bond with employees to maintain OCB (**Dahal, 2013**). This study focuses on relationship strength, the value of money, economic value, and other facilities that also play an important role in maintaining the commitment to the institution.

Finally, we found from the research that Relationship quality, value, and strength all are associated with OCB (**Groth, 2005**). However, institutes use different dimensions to engage the students and to achieve the trust and commitment of students. A higher level of relationship quality is the only way directly associated with student OCB.

Administrative Implication:

The study shows that relationship is the key source for firms to achievement of Student OCB. The student-institute relationship is based on relationship value. However, researchers have found in many research about superior value input will give quality to a relationship. Also, the evaluation of any institute is based on the value of money, core benefits, brand image, trust, and the relationship-based activities performed by the institute. Support services in academic institutions like mentoring, grooming, counseling, etc. always give special support to the students and they feel the value for money for their

institutional brand. Relationship between students and institutions provides different relationship values, also provide the cost of saving, and create a strong bond.

Study shows that relationship quality is strongly connected to relationship value and strength. All the above three relationship dimensions form student OCB. However; for the maintenance of these relationships only quality maintenance is not enough, a high level of relationship support and values should be transferred to students, providing better support services, and a smooth environment for learning in the institute, together create a high level of relationship quality and strength. For creating the Student OCB, high levels of relationship value and quality are equally important. Engagement of the students with the institution is more important to increase the relationship quality, students' perception of the high level of quality and value should be matched with the institution's engagement process; which will increase the Student OCB.

Limitations:

The present study acknowledges several avenues for future research as potential limitations. These suggestions aim to enhance the understanding of the relationship model of value, strength, and quality in the context of Student OCB, as well as explore additional dimensions and extend the research to different industries and populations. The identified areas for future research include:

Mediation and moderation effects; Future research can delve into exploring the mediating and moderating effects of quality on Student OCB and relationship value. Investigating these effects can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the underlying dynamics and mechanisms of the relationship model.

Customer relationship in different industries; While the current study focuses on student or student relationships in academic institutions, future research can expand the scope to include various types of organizations and industries (**Cheung, 2010**). This broader perspective would provide insights into the similarities and differences in relationship dynamics across different contexts. Comparative analysis across cities and countries; the study's limitation lies in its narrow focus on a single city within a specific country. Future research can overcome this limitation by conducting comparative analyses across different cities and even countries (**Cheung, 2010**). This approach would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship model's variations and generalizability.

Relationship between variables and demographic factors; Research could explore the relationship between variables such as relationship value, quality, and strength, and demographic variables like age, gender, etc. Examining these associations can provide valuable insights into how different demographic factors influence the dynamics of Student OCB and relationship building. Extension to alumni and other degree courses; while the present study focuses on current students of professional courses, future research can expand the scope to include alumni and students from different degree programs. This broader perspective would enable a comprehensive examination of Student OCB and its impact across various segments of the academic community (**Dahal, 2013**).

CONCLUSION

Hence the study recommends that awareness of the antecedents of Student OCB, known as Relationship Value (RV), Relationship Quality (RQ), and Relationship Strength (RS) is relevant within the higher learning institution for effective student organizational citizenship behavior. Since the market scenario changes and expectations from the organizations grow new changes need to be planned for students who are the key and vital sources of any educational institute. Consequently, results from this study show that the extent to which students interact with the institution at large, its faculty and fellow students as well as the learning environment has a significant impact on Student OCB. This research aims to fill a significant literature gap that focuses on the explored means through which the examined relationship dynamics can enhance students' attitudes and promote the right democratic morale in learning institutions. Given the fact that education institutions have to operate within a dynamic context that continues to change, for instance through the developments in technology, problems, complexities, and values, the formation of values-oriented and quality relationships is even more relevant. Hence, institutions will be able to increase students' attention and satisfaction rates and obtain a competitive advantage in the market. Furthermore, on this foundation, it can be produced the rendition of continuous and sustainable support to the environment and expectations regarding the students' learning and development have to be provided for the improvement of educational facilities' performance.

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